

LEGAL PROTECTION TO SENIOR CITIZENS IN INDIA WITH REFERENCE TO THEIR MAINTENANCE

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ABSTRACT:-

This article examines the legal provisions and judicial pronouncements regarding the maintenance and welfare of senior citizens in India and discusses the problems in applying and implementing such laws. India's aging population needs strong legal frameworks to ensure their maintenance and welfare.

KEYWORDS:-

India, aging population, senior citizens, maintenance laws, welfare, legal framework and parental rights.

INTRODUCTION:-

In the ancient and medieval era, the families used to take care of their elderly members. Nowadays, urban lifestyles and modernization are rapidly increasing. On that count, the mindset of families is changing. Moreover, the concept of a joint family is withering. In the year 2025, the life expectancy of males and females in the world is 73.5. At the same time, the life expectancy of males and females in India is 72.48.¹ In India, the population of older people is more. Therefore, the laws play a crucial role in protecting them. In order to maintain senior citizens, India has enacted the laws. One of the objects of such laws is to maintain their dignity as well.

LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR SENIOR CITIZENS:-

Manu Smriti and Dharmashastras outlined family obligations including parental care. In 1772, Governor General Warren Hastings introduced Hindu Law for Hindus and Muslim Law for Muslims. Sections 488 to 490 of Chapter XXXVI of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898 dealt with the maintenance right of wives and children in British India. The parents were not included in Sections 488 to 490 of Chapter XXXVI of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898. The parents were not entitled to claim the maintenance under Sections 488 to 490 of Chapter XXXVI of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898. Before coming into force the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023, Sections 125 to 128 of Chapter IX of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 dealt with the maintenance. The legislature added the words father or mother in Section 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973. Thus, the parents were entitled to claim maintenance under Sections 125 to 128 of Chapter IX of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973. Now Sections 144 to 147 of Chapter X of the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023 and Sections 20 to 28 of Chapter III of the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act, 1956 deal with the maintenance. The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita,

¹ <https://www.worldometers.info/demographics/life-expectancy/>

2023 and the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act, 1956 give the right of maintenance to parents. So far as parents and senior citizens are concerned, the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 deals with their maintenance and is guaranteed and recognized under the Constitution. Though the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 gives a right to claim monetary relief to aggrieved women, but male senior citizens are not covered therein.

The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 :-

- **Maintenance:** The fundamental needs of human beings such as food, clothing, residence and medical attendance and treatment are covered in the definition of maintenance.
- **Senior Citizens:** A citizen of India who has attained the age of 60 years or above is a senior citizen.
- **Parent:** The definition of parent contains father or mother. The biological, adoptive or step-father or step-mother are also covered in the definition of parent. There are no criteria that a father or mother should be a senior citizen.
- **Maintenance Tribunal:** An officer not below the rank of Sub-Divisional Officer is the presiding officer of the Maintenance Tribunal to adjudicate the maintenance applications of senior citizens and parents.
- **Appellate Tribunal:** An officer not below the rank of District Magistrate is the presiding officer of the Appellate Tribunal to hear appeals against the orders of the Maintenance Tribunal.
- **Right to Maintenance:** Senior citizens including parents unable to maintain themselves can claim the maintenance against their major children. Childless senior citizens can claim the maintenance against their legal heirs who are not minors and are in possession of or would inherit their property after their death.
- **Application for Maintenance:** A senior citizen or parent or any other person or organization authorized by him can make an application to the Maintenance Tribunal for maintenance. The Tribunal is also empowered to take cognizance *suo motu* to grant the maintenance to senior citizens or parents.
- **Procedure of Tribunal:** The Maintenance Tribunal is empowered to follow summary procedures in trying the maintenance applications and has all the powers of the Civil Court. It has to determine the maintenance amount after giving an opportunity of being heard to both parties. It has to decide the maintenance application within 90 days from the date of service of notice to the other side and if not possible, 30 days can be extended. There is also a provision for interim maintenance during the pendency of the maintenance proceeding.
- **Order of Maintenance:** If senior citizens or parents are unable to maintain themselves, the Maintenance Tribunal is empowered to order their children or relatives to pay them a monthly maintenance not exceeding ten thousand rupees.
- **Alteration in allowance:** The Maintenance Tribunal is empowered to alter the maintenance ordered if there is a misrepresentation, mistake of fact, or a change in the circumstances of any person receiving a monthly allowance.
- **Cancellation of Maintenance Order:** The Maintenance Tribunal has to cancel or vary the maintenance order passed by it if there is any decision of a competent Civil Court in relation to the maintenance dispute.

- **Enforcement of Maintenance Order:** The maintenance order passed by the Maintenance Tribunal can be executed in accordance with the procedure given under Section 125(3) and 128 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973. If the children or relatives fail to comply with the maintenance order, the Maintenance Tribunal is empowered to issue a warrant against them and can sentence them to imprisonment for a term up to one month or until payment of the maintenance allowance.
- **Appeal:** If senior citizens or parents are aggrieved by an order of the Maintenance Tribunal, they are at liberty to prefer an appeal before the Appellate Tribunal within 60 days from the date of the order. The remedy of such appeal is provided to the senior citizens or parents only and not to their children or relatives. The decision of the Appellate Tribunal is final. There is no provision for a second appeal.
- **Legal Representation:** The parties before the Maintenance Tribunal or the Appellate Tribunal are not permitted to be represented by legal practitioner. But the officer not below the rank of District Social Welfare Officer is permitted to represent the Senior Citizens or parents only and not their children or relatives.
- **Jurisdiction:** The maintenance proceedings can be made against the children or relatives in any district where anyone of them reside or last resided.
- **Conciliation:** During the pendency of the maintenance proceeding, the Tribunal can refer the dispute to a Conciliation Officer for amicable settlement.
- **Establishment of Old Age Homes:** The State Government has to set up and maintain old age homes for needy senior citizens.
- **Healthcare for Senior Citizens:** The State Government has to provide facilities for the treatment of elderly diseases of senior citizens and to provide them the beds in Government hospitals. It has also to provide them free medical services and priority treatment in government hospitals.
- **Protection Against Neglect:** Provision of punishment to those who abandon the senior citizens.
- **Protection of Life and Property of Senior Citizens:** The Government has to take care of the life and property of the senior citizens.

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (the Cr.P.C.):-

- Sections 125 to 128 of Chapter IX of the Cr.P.C. provide a remedy to the parents who cannot maintain themselves. They are at liberty to claim the maintenance amount from their children by invoking the provisions of Sections 125 to 128 of the Cr.P.C.
- The Courts of Judicial Magistrates are empowered to deal with such cases.
- The Courts of Judicial Magistrates are empowered to order interim maintenance or monthly allowances of any amount. No specific cap is given.
- **Alteration in allowance:** The Courts of Judicial Magistrates are empowered to alter the maintenance order if there is a change in the circumstances.
- **Enforcement of Maintenance Order:** If the maintenance order passed by the Court of Judicial Magistrate is not complied with, it is empowered to issue a warrant against whom the order is passed and can sentence them to imprisonment for a term up to one month or until payment of the maintenance allowance.
- **Revision:** There is no provision for appeal. But any aggrieved party by an order of the Court of Judicial Magistrate is at liberty to file a revision before the Sessions Court.

- Legal Representation: The parties before the Court of Judicial Magistrate or Sessions Court are at liberty to be represented by a legal practitioner.
- Jurisdiction: The maintenance proceedings can be made against a person in any district where he resides.
- The Cr.P.C. was replaced by the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023 w.e.f. 01/07/2024. Therefore, Sections 125 to 128 of Chapter IX of the Cr.P.C. have become ineffective.

The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023 (the B.N.N.S.):-

- Sections 144 to 147 of the B.N.N.S. deal with the order of maintenance of wives, children and parents.
- Sections 144 to 147 of the B.N.N.S. are the same that of Sections 125 to 128 of the Cr.P.C.
- Sections 144 to 147 of the B.N.N.S. provide a remedy to the parents who cannot maintain themselves.
- The parents can claim the maintenance amount from their children by invoking the provision of Sections 144 to 147 of the B.N.N.S.
- The Courts of Judicial Magistrates are empowered to deal with such cases and to order interim maintenance or monthly allowances of any amount. Here also no specific cap is given.
- Alteration in allowance: The Courts of Judicial Magistrates are empowered to alter the maintenance order if there is a change in the circumstances.
- Enforcement of Maintenance Order: If the maintenance order passed by the Court of Judicial Magistrate is not complied with, it is empowered to issue a warrant against whom the order is passed and can sentence them to imprisonment for a term up to one month or until payment of the maintenance allowance.
- Revision: There is no provision for appeal. But any aggrieved party by an order of the Court of Judicial Magistrate is at liberty to file a revision before the Sessions Court.
- Legal Representation: The parties before the Court of Judicial Magistrate or Sessions Court are at liberty to be represented by a legal practitioner.
- Jurisdiction: The maintenance proceedings can be made against any person in any district where he or his father or mother resides.
- It is pertinent to note that the parents are entitled to claim the maintenance under either of the B.N.N.S. or the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 but not under both.

The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956:-

- Section 20 of the Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act, 1956 provides a remedy to the aged or infirm parents who cannot maintain themselves.
- The Hindu aged or infirm parents can claim the maintenance amount from their children.
- This is a civil remedy and the Civil Court is empowered to deal with such cases.
- The parents include a childless step-mother as well.
- The claim for maintenance can be charged on the estate of a person against whom the claim is made.

- The decree for maintenance can be executed by the detention in civil prison of the person against whom the decree is passed or by attachment and sale of his property or by both vide Order 21 of the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908.

The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005:-

- Under the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, only a woman is an aggrieved person.
- If any woman having a domestic relationship with the respondent alleges to have been subjected to any act of domestic violence, she can approach the Court of Judicial Magistrate by invoking the provisions of the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005.
- The aggrieved woman can seek various reliefs including monetary relief under the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005.
- The monetary relief means the expenses incurred and the losses suffered by the aggrieved woman as a result of the domestic violence.
- The orders for monetary relief can be executed in accordance with the procedure given in the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973.
- Though the aggrieved woman includes a woman of any age, but it does not contain a male.

JUDICIAL PRONOUNCEMENTS:-

- The Supreme Court of India in the following judgments held that the Right to Life includes the Right to Livelihood and Shelter-
 1. Olga Tellis *Versus* Bombay Municipal Corporation²
 2. Francis Coralie *Versus* Union Territory of Delhi³
 3. Board of Trustees of the Port of Bombay *Versus* Dilipkumar Raghavendranath Nadkarni⁴
 4. Chameli Singh *Versus* State of U.P.⁵
- On 28th January 2025, Kerala High Court in Unneen *Versus* Shoukathali & Ors. held that it is both a moral duty and legal obligation of the son to provide sustenance to their parents in their old age even if they somehow manage to maintain themselves with the financial support of relatives or friends.⁶
- Right to life is the right to livelihood and shelter under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution.

CHALLENGES AND IMPLEMENTATION:-

Despite strong legal provisions, implementation of providing maintenance to the parents and senior citizens is a challenge. Many elderly citizens struggle to access legal remedies due to lack of awareness or social stigma. Even though the laws are good, they are not always enforced well. Many elderly people don't know

² AIR 1986 SC 180 <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/709776/>

³ (1981)1 SCC 608 <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/78536/>

⁴ AIR 1983 109 <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1787020/>

⁵ AIR 1996 SC 1051 <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/64823282/>

⁶ https://drive.google.com/viewerng/viewer?url=https://www.verdictum.in/pdf_upload/2025-ker-6982-1687693.pdf

their rights or face social stigma. The maintenance proceedings are not decided within given time limit. Section 21 of the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 specifies that the State Government has to take all measures to ensure that the provisions of this Act are given wide publicity through public media. But no such publicity is seen to be given to the provisions of this Act. Section 22 of the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 confers powers and imposes the duties on the District Magistrate to ensure that the provisions of this Act are properly carried out. But the District Magistrates are busy in their administrative work. They do not have time and interest in such type of work. Section 31 of the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 specifies that the Central Government has to make periodic review and monitor the progress of the implementation of the provisions of this Act by the State Governments. But no such review is seen to be taken.

RECOMMENDATIONS:-

Strengthening awareness campaigns and ensuring swift legal action can enhance the effectiveness of the laws relating to maintenance of parents and senior citizens. More awareness and quick legal action can help protect senior citizens better. Government should take initiatives to strengthen the legal awareness about the rights of senior citizens. Free legal services should be provided to elderly individuals seeking maintenance. Section 22 of the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 should be amended and such powers should be conferred to the District Legal Services Authority.

CONCLUSION:-

India's legal framework provides healthy protection for senior citizens, particularly in terms of maintenance and welfare. However, societal responsibility and awareness play a crucial role in ensuring that elderly individuals receive the care and dignity they deserve.

REFERENCES:-

1. The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007
2. The Constitution of India, 1950
3. The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023
4. The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973
5. The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898
6. The Hindu Adoptions and Maintenance Act, 1956
7. The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908
8. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005